

FLOWER SHOP ONLINE SUPPORTING SYSTEM

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Abstract. The flower industry has grown significantly, with many people seeking beautiful and personalized flowers. This project introduces the Online Flower Shop Website, an easy-to-use e-commerce platform designed to simplify buying flowers. The website offers a variety of products, including flower bouquets, artificial bouquets, handmade bouquets, seasonal bouquets, and money bouquets. Its main goal is to provide a straightforward, secure, and enjoyable online shopping experience. Additionally, the website aims to cater to various occasions, making it easy for customers to find the perfect floral arrangement for any event. With a user-friendly interface and a wide selection, it ensures that every customer can effortlessly select and purchase flowers that suit their needs and preferences.

Keywords: online flower shop, e-commerce, product management, user-friendly

INTRODUCTION

In today's digital world, an effective flower shop online supporting system is important for providing a smooth shopping experience and easy management. This project aims to create a reliable platform that supports various tasks like product management, customer interactions, and order processing. The motivation behind this project is to make shopping convenient for customers and managing the store simple for administrators. By using modern design principles and technology, the Flower Shop Online Supporting System aims to enhance efficiency, increase customer satisfaction, and support business growth.

PROBLEM

The project focuses on core features like adding and managing products, implementing a price range slider, and integrating essential functionalities. The system also includes an admin dashboard for managing orders and products. The goal is to move from traditional shopping methods to a more streamlined online process, offering a convenient and interactive shopping experience for customers and easy management for administrators.

APPROACH

Users can start by accessing the platform, where they have the option to either register as new users or log in if they already have an account. Once logged in, they can explore various features of the website. Users can browse through different product categories, view

Accepted Date: 25.10.2024

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detailed information about each item, add items to their wish list or shopping cart, and adjust the quantity of products they wish to purchase. The flowchart illustrates the user's journey from exploring the website to proceeding to checkout, selecting a payment method, and placing an order. It also includes options for users to view their order history, send messages to customer support and eventually log out. This visual representation ensures that all potential user actions are accounted for providing a clear and organized structure for navigation the online store. The following flowchart shows the system flow for the user interface.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram for user

Admins can log in to access the admin dashboard, where they can manage various aspects of the e-commerce platform. The flowchart details actions such as viewing the dashboard for an overview of key metrics, managing products by adding, updating, or deleting items, and organizing product categories. Admins can also manage customer orders, update order statuses, and handle customer messages. Additionally, they can manage user accounts by adding new users, editing existing ones, and setting permissions. The flowchart ends with the admin logging out, ensuring a secure exit from the system. The following flowchart shows the system flow for the administrator interface.

Figure 2: System Flow Diagram for Admin

The Database Diagram illustrates the structure of an online flower shop's database. The central User entity connects to key tables such as Orders, Wishlist, Cart, Message, and Reviews, linking user data to shop interactions. The Products table manages available items and integrates with Wishlist and Cart, supporting the buying process. Orders capture transaction details, while Replies and Category tables facilitate message management and product classification, ensuring a well-organized system for both user and admin functions.

Figure 3: Database Design

RESULTS

The online flower shop project has effectively delivered a user-friendly platform that simplifies the process of finding and purchasing flowers. Key features include detailed product views, an intuitive checkout process, and efficient order management, which enhance the overall shopping experience. The system architecture, including a well-structured database, supports seamless user interaction and streamlined administrative functions. By employing modern design and technology, the platform has improved accessibility and convenience for users, allowing them to easily browse products, manage their carts and wishlists, and complete transactions smoothly.

Figure 4: Implementation of the System

CONCLUSION

The online flower shop project has effectively delivered a user-friendly platform that simplifies the process of finding and purchasing flowers. Key features, including detailed product views, an intuitive checkout process, and efficient order management, enhance the overall shopping experience. By using modern design and technology, the platform has improved accessibility and convenience for users. Looking ahead, there are opportunities to further enhance the shop by incorporating personalized recommendations, expanding mobile functionality, and integrating additional features to better meet customer needs and stay competitive in the market.

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Accepted Date: 25.10.2024
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